

Globalization In India: The Key Issues

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Abstract

Globalization in India refers to the increasing integration of the Indian economy, society, and culture with the rest of the world. India has been actively participating in the process of globalization since the early 1990s when the country adopted economic reforms known as liberalization, privatization, and globalization (LPG). Globalization has transformed various aspects of Indian society, economy, and culture. It has expanded trade and investment, fostered the growth of the IT and services sector, and facilitated cultural exchange. However, it has also brought challenges and inequalities that need to be addressed for more inclusive and sustainable development.

Keywords: Globalization, Indian Economy, Social Inequality, Information Technology, Privatization

Introduction

The term 'globalization' has been discussed by social scientists, policymakers, and opinion leaders for more than two decades. The distinguishing feature of present-day globalization is that it is a product of late capitalism. The term 'Late Capitalism' is used to describe capitalism after the Second World War (Desai 1987:67) According. to Anthony Giddens, "Globalization refers to the fact that we all live in one world, so that individuals, groups and nations become interdependent." Globalization is associated with a particular ideology, namely neo-liberalism. Neo-Liberalism asserts the primacy of the market and opening up of the economy of all nations to free trade, privatization and withdrawal of the state from regulation of economic activities. Globalization in India started in 1981 when India took a massive loan of 5 billion SDRs from the IMF.

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But it is in the second phase, when India took another massive loan of \$2.5 billion in 1991 to cope with the balance of payments crisis that globalization in India actually started. In line with the neo-liberal philosophy, India started economic reforms. The state started withdrawing from economic activities, some PSUs were disinvested and more are in the pipeline, import substitution was substituted for a liberalized trade regime, and the country's resources in the spectrum, coal, etc., were thrown open to be exploited by foreign business houses and so on. In this lecture, I will discuss some key contemporary issues regarding globalization in India, namely, (1) Globalization & Employment (2) Globalization & Higher Education (3) Globalization & Industrial Unrest (4) Globalization & FDI in retail (5) Globalization & Corruption.

Defining Globalization

In his Keynote Address to the 5th Refresher Course in Social Studies at the UGC Academic Staff College, The University of Burdwan, on 24th August, 2012, Prof. T.K. Oomen, Emeritus Professor of Sociology, Jawaharlal Nehru University, spoke of the need for social scientists to study globalization. But though the term has been discussed from different angles, a consensus still eludes social scientists. As Andrew Hurrell has observed in *The Oxford Concise Dictionary of Politics*, Globalization resists any single or simple definition. It has multiple meanings. He has defined the term as follows: "Globalization is about the universal processes or set of processes which generate a multiplicity of linkages and interconnections which transcend the states and societies which make up the modern world system." (Hurrell: 2003, p.223. Bold italics mine) He observes that there are distinctions between economic and political readings of globalization. There are also distinctions between globalization, internationalization, westernization and modernization. This definition is, however, very abstract and overarching.

A more comprehensive definition is offered by Gordon Marshall et.al. According to Gordon Marshall et.al, "Contemporary globalization theory argues that globalization comprises two entirely contradictory processes of homogenization and differentiation; that there is a complex interaction between localism and globalism; and that there are powerful movements of resistance against globalization process". (Marshall, Gordon et.al: 1998, p.258. Bold italics mine") They argue that the excessive use of the term in sociology has emptied it of any analytical or explanatory value.

According to Anthony Giddens, "Globalization refers to the fact that we all live in one world so that individuals, groups and nations become interdependent" (Giddens, 2006: 50.). Giddens points out some factors leading to globalization.

These are :

- 1) Technology. The increasing use of Information and communication technology, i.e., computers, Internet, mobile, etc.
- 2) Economic factors. Globalization is driven by integration of the world's economy.
- 3) The weightless economy in which information technology plays a major role.
- 4) Political change. The collapse of the Soviet Union and socialism throughout Eastern Europe played an important role in ushering in globalization. Along with this, we find growth of mechanism of international and regional mechanisms of government. We also find International Government Organizations and International Non-Government Organizations.

The above definitions represent a set of western concepts of globalization. But such definitions are not considered satisfactory by Indian economist, Sunanda Sen. He observes that output alone cannot be seen as an indicator of the success of globalization. It is important to examine its impact on the quality of life. Sen dwelt on the following eight aspects of globalization which he sees as very important.

- 1) Globalization has resulted in the emergence of a three-tiered structure in society. -the elites, the well-to-do middle class, and the marginalized. The growing discontent of the marginalized with globalization cannot be wished away.
- 2) Globalization is neo-colonialism in a new format. From a formal institutional structure designed to maintain hegemony over the third-world countries, powerful Western nations have developed informal surveillance mechanisms over the third world.
- 3) Globalization is market driven but the market ignores the need for a decent level of living.
- 4) Globalization is technology driven but only the rich and well-to-do can afford the technology. Hence technology creates a chasm between the rich and poor.
- 5) Globalization is technology driven but this technology is being used against labor. The rapid rise in the use of technology has not been matched by the corresponding rise in the number of jobs.
- 6) Globalization is also finance driven. The integration of the financial sector in the age of globalization has resulted in the domination of finance over manufacturing with consequent adverse effects on employment.
- 7) The supremacy of finance also means domination of the US dollar in the world market.

This adds to the military hegemony already being enjoyed by the USA.

8) Globalization has resulted in increasing inequality, both within and across nations. (Sen: 2009:2-6)

Given the above features of globalization, the author argues that “Globalization may trigger off a path of growth sans development” (Sen, loc. cit,p.8) How far is this true of India?

Reasons For India Embracing Globalization

Why did India globalize? The answer lies in the decline of the Indian economy. Throughout the eighties, India's economy declined. A combination of factors brought about this decline that ultimately led to a serious balance of payments problem. The IMF loan in

1981 was due to balance of payment difficulties and it started the first wave of liberalization. Sen identifies four major factors behind the economic decline of Third World countries. Among these are

1. Sharp cuts in concessional development assistance from rich nations;
2. Decline in net exports of Third World countries to developed countries;
3. Steep rise in the import bill for oil;
4. Recourse to IMF Loan as a last resort which came with high conditionalities. India's balance of payments crisis compelled her to approach the IMF for a loan of \$2.5 billion in 1991. The proposed loan is among the largest that the I.M.F. has given to India in recent times and followed a declaration by the then Prime Minister Chandra Shekhar that he had authorized senior officials to negotiate such assistance in Washington¹

Political Economy of Liberalized India

Thus, India was compelled to globalize. India's globalization was termed 'liberalization'. Thanks to globalization, India's economic policy underwent radical and irreversible changes. The salient features of the 'New Economic Policy' and its attendant politics is given in Table 1. Our first Prime Minister, Jawaharlal Nehru, was greatly impressed by the massive development strides that the Soviet Union achieved under Socialism. His plan was to replicate this model in India with some modifications. The Five-Year plans which he started were based on the Soviet model. He also wanted to make India economically self-sufficient by building a strong industrial base. And the public sector

was to play a leading role, occupying the commanding heights of the economy. Nehru also wanted to pursue an independent foreign policy. Along with President Nasser of Egypt, Josif Broz Tito, and some other leaders, he started the Non-Aligned Movement that steered clear of both the American and Soviet blocs during the Cold War. Nehru also understood the necessity of peace for development and worked for world peace.

But, unlike Stalin's Russia, India never made much progress on solving key development issues like equitable distribution of resources among the people. Excessive bureaucratization and politicization brought in its wake problems like corruption and patronage. Nehru and his successors could not solve problems of inequality, illiteracy, poverty, unemployment and hunger.

With India being forced to take a loan from the IMF owing to our precarious foreign exchange reserves, the Government of India had to abide by the stringent conditions set forth by the IMF. Instead of autarchy, the doors of our country have been thrown open to imports of all kinds. Foreign Direct Investment is welcomed, notwithstanding the fact that foreigners also bring with them a culture with which Indians are not familiar. Instead of acting independently in international relations, India is acting like a subordinate partner of the USA. To cite an example, we are obeying the diktats of USA not to buy oil from Iran. India is also increasingly spending more money to buy and develop sophisticated weapons including missiles, AWACS, and nuclear weapons than on developmental activities.

Table 1. Nehruvianism vis-a vis Liberalization

Nehruvianism (Independence to 1990)	Liberalization(1991 onward)
I. Basic Philosophy Democratic Socialism Features: a) Faith in democratic values b) Removal of poverty c) Reduction of inequalities in income and wealth d) Equal opportunities for all e) Faith in mixed economy	1. Basic Philosophy Liberalization Features: a) Faith in democratic values b) Privatization c) Encouraging multinational corporations to enter the country d) Encouraging imports by removing tariff barriers e) The model followed IMF-World Bank prescription of stabilization and structural adjustment. II ECONOMIC POLICY

Nehruvianism (Independence to 1990)	Liberalization(1991 onward)
<p>b) Dominant role of public sector</p> <p>c) Check on monopolistic restrictions through MRTP ACT.</p> <p>d) Fiscal policies aimed at reducing inequalities of income and wealth through progressive taxation</p> <p>e) Import substitution through indigenizing everything, including foreign bred high yielding variety of seeds, transfer of technology in key sectors like defence production.</p> <p>Foreign Policy</p> <p>Non-Alignment</p> <p>Peaceful coexistence.</p>	<p>a) Heavy industrialization</p> <p>b) Privatization. Private sector allowed to make inroads into areas reserved for the public sector. Disinvestment of public sector enterprises.</p> <p>c) Ceiling of assets under MRTP ACT abolished. Concentration of economic power encouraged.</p> <p>d) Foreign direct investment encouraged in high priority areas.</p> <p>Imports by removing tariff barriers.</p> <p>Foreign Policy</p> <p>Non-alignment diluted. India plays subordinate role vis-à-vis USA.</p> <p>Peaceful coexistence replaced by war mongering.</p>

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THE KEY ISSUES

In this lecture we will discuss certain key issues with regard to globalization in contemporary India. These are as follows:

- 1) Globalization & Employment Scenario in India
- 2) Globalization & Higher Education in India
- 3) Globalization & Industrial Unrest in India
- 4) Globalization & FDI in retail in India
- 5) Globalization &Corruption in India

1) Globalization & Employment Scenario in India

The ideology of Globalization has laid stress on privatization, cutbacks in social welfare on part of government, and faith in the free market as a solution to the problems of employment and human happiness. Here we will discuss the role of globalization in promoting employment opportunities. We have seen that Sunanda Sen has criticized globalization. He says that new technology, instead of creating more jobs at better terms, often today displaces labour. (Sen, 2009, p.5). In a paper, Albert Christopher Dhas and Mary Jacqueline Helen analyzed the impact of globalization on jobs in India. Citing official statistics they show that in the pre-globalization period (1983-1993-94) the unemployment rate showed a decline from 8.3% to 5.99 %. But the unemployment rate subsequently increased in the age of Globalization to 7.32 till 1999-2000. Sector wise, some sectors such as agriculture, mining, quarrying, electricity, manufacturing, there has been a decrease in employment, But in construction, hotel, storage and communications, an overall increase in employment has been recorded.

On further analysis of the employment scenario, Dhas and Helen make following observations:

- In 2001, the total workforce in the country was 402 millions. Of them, 313 million are main workers and 89 million are marginal workers. Of these 313 million main workers,
- 285 million, i.e., 91% work in the unorganized sector.
- According to the Alternative Survey Group, the share of the organized workforce in India fell from 8.33% in 1983 to 7.65% in 1999-2000. The corresponding share of the unorganized workforce rose from 91.67% in 1983 to 92.65% in 1999-2000.
- The decline in the public sector as a result of the economic 'reforms' pursued by the
- Government of India has contributed to the decline in organized sector workers.
- In the context of the declining growth rate in employment generation in the organized sector and no scope for creating additional jobs, the authors argue that the additional workforce will either have to remain self employed or become casual workers.
- Casual workers are highly exploited .They get low wages, have no benefits like medical benefits, pension, gratuity, etc.

From this analysis Dhas and Helen conclude that globalization has an adverse effect on the employment scenario in India. ".....it can be argued that the benefits of economic reforms on the Indian economy would get achieved, only if the negative impacts on employment are settled or neutralized"³. Dhas and Helen's work fits in with the thesis that globalization is anti-labour.

The year 2008 heralded bad times for neo-liberalism. A global economic depression set in at this period of time. If America sneezes, the whole world catches cold. The economic downturn in the West was heralded by the sub-prime mortgage crisis that hit the American banks. Since then depression started in many countries. India was not fully immune to this crisis. Thanks to the Left parties, which opposed total capitulation of the Indian government to IMF dictated neo-liberalism, India managed to fend off the economic shocks. Yet, the global economic depression hit India's IT sector. Job hopping in this sector has been significantly reduced, reports T. E. Raja Simhan. An ASSOCHAM survey found that job creation has been significantly reduced in all IT companies. "An uncertain global economic environment together with cross-currency fluctuation has compelled the employees to adopt a wait-and-watch policy leading to a sharp decline in the attrition levels in the IT-BPO sector that has been grappling with talent crunch due to shortage of competent managers at middle and senior levels for quite some time," said D. S. Rawat, Assocham Secretary-General, releasing the findings of the study recently⁴

Therefore we find that India's partial integration with the world's economic system in the age of globalization has had an adverse effect on jobs. We found that compared to the pre-globalization period, globalization has less jobs to offer the common man. Jobs in the organized sector have decreased. Jobs in the unorganized sector increased due mainly to employers' preference for contract jobs. The worldwide economic depression has further depressed the job market.

2) Globalization & Higher Education in India

India is a country with one of the second largest institutional higher education system in the world.

Consider the following data –

- India has more than 300 universities. Out of these 95 are deemed to be universities, 13 institutions of national importance. We have 19 central universities and 203 state universities. In addition 5 institutions have been established under state legislation acts.
- We have 16,885 colleges. These include 203 Autonomous colleges.
- ☐ India also has a huge teacher population. 4.37 lakhs teaching Faculty were employed in
- 2004.

- India has a huge student population. At the beginning of the academic year in 2004, we had 99.53 lakh students prosecuting higher education, of which 12.97 lakh (13.3 per cent) were studying in university departments and 86.57 lakh (86.97 per cent) in colleges affiliated to universities⁵.

In the present-day neo-liberal set up, India presents a lucrative market for foreign players. But will globalization in higher education be beneficial to India?

Before we discuss this question, let us first examine the GATT regulations regarding higher education. Under GATT regulations, all countries have to submit their educational schedules under five sub-sectors of education and four modes of supply of education.

- The five sub-sectors of education are: Primary Education; Secondary Education; Higher Education; Adult Education and Other Education.
- The four modes of supply of education are Cross-Border Supply; Consumption Abroad; Commercial Presence/Franchisee and Twinning Programmes.

As Mithilesh Kumar Singh aptly pointed out, "The idea behind this is the creation of an open, global marketplace where services, like education, can be traded to the highest bidder."⁶

How far will globalization benefit a country's education system? What will be the role of our universities in the global education system? Over this there is no consensus either among Western educationists or Third world educationists.

First let us look at the views of American university leaders. According to Van R. Wood, University leaders interviewed tended to express a common vision that institutions of higher education have two central responsibilities in society today, including 1) enlightening and preparing, not just their students, but their respective communities as a whole for the challenges and opportunities brought on by globalization, and 2) being the major supplier of the intellectual capital (knowledge workers) that communities need to survive and prosper in the era of globalization⁷. From Wood's research, we find that

American university leaders' perceptions of the role of the university are a combination of idealism and pragmatism. In an earlier paper, Philip G. Altbach explored the relation between colonialism and local political forces in developing countries. He argued that even those countries which were not colonized have been influenced by western education systems. (Altbach, 1989).

Indian intellectuals' perceptions of the role of globalization in higher education differ from their American counterparts. Das (2007:47-67) argues that access to higher education in India is severely restricted. He is critical of the World Bank view that higher education is a non-merit good and traces the consequences of such an approach to funding, finance and access.

Is Foreign Direct Investment in Higher Education desirable? According to Samuel Paul, founder of Public Affairs Centre, Bangalore, and former director of IIM, Ahmedabad, "The entry of foreign education providers may also help stimulate our existing educational system to rethink its ways of working. Competition rather than fiat is the best way to accomplish this much needed transformation. The downside of the new policy is that access to the foreign providers' programmes will be dominated by the elite segment of the population, as fees and other conditions of entry will tend to favour them."⁸ He, however, does not have a high hope of highly reputed institutions opening shop in India. According to M S Narasimhan, Professor of Finance and Chairperson of Executive Education at IIM, Bangalore, since public funding is difficult to sustain in the long run, private players may be admitted. But, he is in favour of some kind of broad control over them including foreign players⁹

Mithilesh Kumar Singh, Senior Research Fellow of Apeejay-Stya Education Research Foundation, raises several uncomfortable sociological issues about the role of globalization in Indian higher education, questions that should be urgently resolved before FDI in higher education is allowed.

- i) Benefits of globalization to the different sections of the society – it is believed to be "far uneven".
- ii) Its role in creating greater social stratification and inequality – widening the gaps between the "haves" and "have not's"
- iii) Its role in destabilizing and distorting the indigenous culture, tradition and values.
- iv) Its role in alienating the youth from its own place by uprooting and at the same time not sure of providing a landing space. And
- v) More than these, its role in facilitating the rich countries to grow richer by drawing the resources from the poor¹⁰.

Thus we find that globalization in higher education is not an unmixed blessing. While Americans may find higher education intellectually enlightening and a source of intellectual capital, in India there is a genuine fear that opening the floodgates to FDI in higher education may pave the way for 2nd rung or third rung education providers swamping the education market, leading to greater social stratification in India, alienating our youth from their roots and making handsome profits in the process of providing education, which they will repatriate to their home country. Only stringent governmental controls over all private players, including foreign players, making them accountable to the country in terms of the quality of education they provide, the fees they charge, the salaries they pay to their staff and the profits they repatriate to their head offices etc. will ensure that FDI in higher education benefits Indians.

3) Globalization & Industrial Unrest in India

Marx and Engels had remarked in the Communist Manifesto (1848) that the history of human societies is the history of class struggles. In this little book they briefly analyzed the growing civil war between the bourgeoisie and the proletariat. That civil war continues in India in the age of globalization. With the onset of globalization in India, governments, whether in the centre or the states have invited Foreign Direct Investment, unmindful of the fact that alien managerial culture may not suit Indian working conditions. And we are now paying the price in terms of industrial unrest. Here are some notable examples of rebellion against foreign big business.

- 2005. Honda workers at Manesar, Haryana, who protested at their colleagues being dismissed for forming a union were brutally beaten up by the police¹¹.
- September 2008. A group of dismissed employees were accused of having lynched L K Chaudhury, the chief executive of Oerlikon-Graziano Transmissions India, the Indian subsidiary of an Italy-based company in Udyog Vihar of Greater Noida¹².
- 2009. Striking workers of Pricol, a Coimbatore-based automobile instruments maker, allegedly attacked and killed the HR vice-president Roy J George¹³.
- July 18, 2012. One senior manager was killed and more than 85 were injured after workers allegedly rioted and set fire to the factory at Manesar in Haryana¹⁴.

In all these cases foreign companies or their Indian subsidiaries were involved. Yet, for sometime industrial unrest was on the decline. "From a whopping 4.5 lakh workers affected due to strikes and lockouts in 2008, the number came down to a mere 90,000 in 2010 so far," report T.K Rohit et.al That's not all. According to data available with the Ministry of Labour, so far 2010 has been a comparatively quieter year with 41 strikes and just 15 lockouts. In comparison, 2008 saw 109 strikes and 148 lockouts. In 2009, it had gone down to 62 strikes although the number of lockouts stood at 172¹⁵.

Why is industrial unrest taking place? "If an employee, who gets one of the best salaries in the country, is going out there, risking his job and huge pay to strike work, something must be definitely wrong. Isn't it?" asks A Soundararanjan, Tamil Nadu's state general secretary of Marxist trade union CITU¹⁶. The following are some of the major reasons why worker unrest is on the rise in India.

1. One of the major reasons for industrial unrest is the negative attitude to unionism on part of employers. Maruti Suzuki faced a strike on this issue in 2010. Except for West Bengal and Maharashtra,

employers are not legally bound to recognize unions. But for workers it is a right which they are not willing to forego. The Indian Trade Unions Act 1926, drafted in the colonial era, gave them the right to form unions. Trade union activists say the increasing number of contractual workers being drafted in by the managements and the issue of recognition of trade unions is a major reason for these protest. The same opinion is voiced by Indian employers. According to B Santhanam, President, Employers' Federation of India, "There are enough Indian companies where trade unionism is very active. The problem is lack of clear procedures for the recognition of unions" 17.

2. Personal animosity may also trigger violence. The Maruti violence was reportedly caused by the alleged disparaging and casteist remarks made at a worker by his supervisor. Sangram Kumar Majhi, the supervisor, allegedly called a worker, Jiya Lal, a Dhed, which was a casteist abuse. During this altercation, the worker allegedly slapped the supervisor and the management decided to suspend the worker without going to the roots of the problem. Jiya Lal, did not accept the suspension. He decided to approach the union, which tried to prevail upon the management to withdraw the suspension against the worker in the interest of good industrial relations. But the management refused to withdraw the suspension while the abusive supervisor was let off, allege the workers. Negotiations broke down and the management allegedly tried to browbeat the workers into submission by setting their hired goons ('bouncers') on them. This was the provocation for the wanton violence that followed. The management, on the other hand, alleged that the violence on part of the workers was unprovoked.¹⁸ Had the management fairly and impartially enquired into the roots of the alleged violence by a single worker, they could have prevented the violence that ensued.

3. Unequal pay may be another sore point in precipitating Industrial unrest. It is alleged that there is a gulf of difference between the pay packets of permanent and contractual workers at Maruti. Maruti has a sizeable number of contractual workers. They get just Rs. 6000/- per month while the permanent workers were paid much better. They get between Rs.18,000/- to Rs.21000/- per month. It is alleged that for the same job contractual worker gets much less than a permanent worker. Anand (2012:26-28) reports: "Since both groups do the same work, the demand for pay parity has grown strong with every passing month, given the rising process and inflation." Such inequity is also a source of acute dissatisfaction at work and may snowball into a protest movement.

4. Bad living conditions also promote discontent. Department of Industrial Policy and Promotion (DIPP) Secretary Saurabh Chandra said at an Assocham function that bad living conditions of contractual workers of Maruti may have precipitated the violence¹⁹.

Solution

What, then is the solution to the problem of industrial unrest ? Recognition of trade unions ? Hire and fire policy ? Armed guards accompanying managers in the workplace in the managerial style adopted by Maruti ?²⁰ I think that recognition of unions will be a step in the right direction. Foreign managements should learn to live with unions which function not only to protect workers' rights but also keep industrial peace. Production at gunpoint is no solution to labour unrest. Calling police power to the aid of the management at the drop of a hat also means that the management has lost its legitimacy in the eyes of the worker and has lost control over the situation. I do not think that so called 'labour market reform' which gives management unlimited powers to hire and fire will lead to lower labour unrest. Even MBA students have been brainwashed in this idea and they have been encouraged to develop it, like the three students of Jamanalal Bajaj Institute of Management Studies, Mumbai, namely, Santosh N Gambhire, Ajitsingh K Patil, Anurag Sinha ²¹. But I agree with them that unless social safety nets are developed for workers, and unless the management adopts labour friendly policies towards recruitment, workers will continue to oppose labour market reform.

I think that all investors, whether Indian or foreign, should be first acquainted with India's labour laws, traditions of the Indian labour movement and Indian style of management. They should try to develop a work culture where managers and workers work for mutual benefit. Foreign employers will greatly benefit from employing Indian social scientists as consultants.

4) Globalization & FDI in retail in India

FDI is now a buzzword. The Government of India is going head over heels to woo foreign investors to bring FDI to India. In the process they are pursuing policies which are not only loathed by the majority of Indians but also spell the danger of the country losing her economic independence.

Prime Minister announces FDI in retail and its impact

Union Commerce and Industry Minister, Anand Sharma, is on record telling Britain's Chancellor of Exchequer, George Osborne that "We are very clear that there is no revisiting on multi-brand retail."²² And now the Prime Minister of India, Manmohan Singh, has announced that he has taken the decision.²³ "51% FDI in multi-brand retailing, in all products, will be permitted," a notification by the department of industrial Policy and

Promotion (DIPP) said. It said the decision will take immediate effect".²⁴

The PM's announcement has kicked off a political maelstrom. Here are a sample of opinions. Firstly let us look at those who are opposing FDI. Mamata Banerjee, chief Minister of West Bengal, who is a vocal opponent of FDI in retail said in her Facebook page that she cannot support anything that is anti people. Her party, the Trinamul Congress, ultimately quit the UPA in protest. Bahujan Samaj Party chief and former Chief Minister of Uttar Pradesh, Kumari Mayavati, condemned the implementation of FDI. Akhilesh Yadav, the Chief Minister of Uttar Pradesh. Mohandas Pal, the BJP spokesman said that this decision was taken by the PM to win some brownie points in the West where he was roundly criticized by the media. Besides, decision was intentionally taken to direct the nation's attention from the scams of the UPA government. Chief Minister of Bihar, Nitish Kumar, said that this decision was suicidal for the UPA government. Criticizing the decision, Sitaram Yechury of CPI(M) said that what the Manmohan Singh government is doing is at the expense of the people. Narendra Modi, the Chief Minister of Gujarat, remarked that small shopkeepers may have to close their establishments due to this decision.²⁵

Supporting this decision, Montek Singh Ahluwalia, Deputy Chairman of the Planning Commission, said that he is glad with thus decision which had long been awaited. The Chairman of Manipal Educational Services said 'Dil mange more'. The Government has to stand up for what it stands for. The allies have their own agenda. 'We need 9% growth'. Venugopal Dhoot, Former President, ASSOCHAM said that some kiranawalas may have a problem and the government should compensate them. But, on the whole, prices will come down. Rakesh Biyani, Joint Managing Director of Pantaloon Retail, said that the decision will solve the supply chain problem that existed in the food chain²⁶.

A section of farmers has welcomed FDI in retail. Farmers have welcomed FDI in retail. That is because it will eliminate the middle men who allegedly take away 45% of the farmer's earnings. Santosh Lata, a farmer says, "Earlier we used to send the vegetables to mandi. It wasn't good. Sometimes we would get Rs 50, sometimes Rs 100. We would not earn any profit. Bharti Walmart has helped us earn profit and we are very happy with it."²⁷

But for how long?

Should we let Wal –Mart in?

The Retail Industry is the sector of economy which is consisted of individuals, stores, commercial complexes, agencies, companies, and organizations, etc., involved in the business of selling or merchandizing diverse finished products or goods to the end-user consumers directly and indirectly²⁸ Foreigners are keenly eyeing the Indian retail market. Kearney (a globally famous international management consultancy), for example, recognized India as the second most alluring and thriving retail destination of the world, among other thirty growing and emerging markets. ²⁹

It is for this reason that retail giants like Wal-Mart are desperate to enter India. Wal- Mart reportedly spent millions of dollars in lobbying the US government to arm-twist India on issues including FDI in India, changes in Indian taxation framework and various other trade-related matters³⁰. But the million dollar questions are : Does Wal-Mart do business honestly? Does Wal-Mart promote local products? Is Wal-Mart a good employer? Before we let Wal-Mart in let us study the impact of this multinational on a developing economy. Mexico may provide an ideal case study

Now let us look at our first question- Does Wal-Mart do business honestly? According to New York Times, the company paid \$24 million to Mexican officials as bribes to capture the Mexican market³¹. What is worse, is that the US Government is willing to turn a Nelson’s eye to such wrong doings by an American multinational. Writing in the New York Times, James R. Stewart wrote: “The Wal-Mart Mexican bribery scheme has all the makings of a gripping criminal prosecution: millions of dollars in illegal payoffs to Mexican government officials and evidence of a cover-up scheme that went all the way to Wal-Mart headquarters in Bentonville, Ark”.³² It is very easy in corporate America to commit crimes and avoid prosecution. 37 of the 57 companies involved in bribery enforcement actions from 2005 to 2010 settled bribery accusations and had no related individuals charged³³. Is there any guarantee that the company will not resort to bribery to capture the Indian market?

Now, our second question, Is Wal-Mart a good employer? Wal-mart has been accused of paying miserable wages. It has been accused of employing an army of unpaid “baggers” at its checkout lines, and has been accused of widespread violation of labor laws. ³⁴

Given its record in Mexico, we legitimately apprehend that the company may take the

advantage of India's huge reserve army of labour to build a slave labour force here also.

Now, our third question is Does Wal-Mart patronize the local market? Wal-Mart has been accused of not having any 'backward linkages' with Mexican manufacturers, i.e., it never buys locally manufactured products. It sells only products manufactured in the United States of America. As a result, the local economy is bound to suffer. Its recent growth has also threatened the existence of traditional Mexican street markets which date to Aztec and Mayan times. It has also been accused of interfering in archeological sites, for instance, Teotihuacan in central Mexico³⁵. Thus Wal-Mart not only threatens the local economy, it also threatens Mexico's tradition and cultural artefacts. If the company is allowed to enter India, it will employ the same techniques as it did in Mexico, and destroy India's local market .

FDI will completely ruin India's retail economy

I fear that FDI will spell complete ruin of India's small businesses. I have seen in Budapest, Hungary, (where I spent a month on a Hungarian scholarship under the Indo- Hungarian Exchange Programme in November, 2011) that big retail chains like Tesco are dominating the market. And they have wiped out Hungarian small business.

But India's small businessmen are determined not to allow FDI in retail. They observed August 9, 2012 as 'Quit FDI Day'³⁶. And, as indicated earlier, they have strong support from a section of our political leaders. But our policy makers are too weak to resist the arm twisting tactics employed by USA and developed countries to open up India's retail markets to the penetration of international finance capital. The 'bold' step taken by Manmohan Singh's government is actually a tame surrender to international finance capital.

5) Globalization &Corruption in India

In Satyajit Ray's film, *Shakha Prosakha*, an honest old man's sons come home when he is critically ill. During their stay in the house, in course of their conversations with each other it emerges that all his sons are not only dishonest, they take pride in their corrupt practices. At the end of the film, when he is about to leave the house the little boy asks his grandfather this momentous question which shocks the old man: "Grandpa, do you know what black and white money is? What money do you have grandpa, red money, green money"?

Writing in the Oxford Concise Dictionary of Politics, Federico Varese defines corruption as follows: "Corruption obtains when an official transfers a benefit to an individual who may or may not be entitled to the benefit in exchange for an illegal Payment". Historically corrupt practices have existed in India for a long time. But it was only since the mid-eighties of the twentieth century that it caught the public eye through a series of high profile scams, like Bofors, Tehelka, etc. Thanks to these scams, India is now rated as one of the most corrupt countries of the world by agencies like transparency International.

As K.N. Panikkar quite rightly pointed out in his Suryanarayana Rao Memorial Lecture, present day corruption is rooted in the possibilities, neo-liberal policies have created for the transfer of public property to private entrepreneurs (Panikkar, 2011 : 36). Three recent scams have done much to dent the image of the government. Manmohan Singh is widely perceived to head one of the most corrupt governments in the world. UPA II has been marked by a plethora of scams. I will just briefly discuss three major scams that have taken place.

1. The 2G Spectrum Scam. This scam broke out in 2010. This scam suggested a careful confluence of the telecom ministry, when it was headed by A. Raja and some big business houses. The Comptroller and Auditor General of India in a report noted: "85 of the 122 licenses were issued to companies, which suppressed facts, disclosed incomplete information, and submitted fictitious documents to DoT and thus used fraudulent means of getting licenses and thereby access to spectrum".³⁷ The scam caused the exchequer a notional loss of Rs.1.76 crore. The case created a public furore inside and outside Parliament and ultimately the Supreme court had to take over the case. Apart from Raja, MPs like Kanimozhi, several powerful bureaucrats and corporate honchos were felled by the case.

2. The Commonwealth Games Scam. This scam involved irregular transfer of funds to foreign companies. "Television channels reported that over £ 4.50 lakh were transferred through a British bank to the A M Films company, said to be a one man show and which was also receiving £ 25,000 a month."³⁸ Documents unearthed by a CBI investigation showed that a firm, Swiss Timing was given a contract (TSR contract) as it "fulfilled every criteria", even before the tender was called. This led to the arrest of the Chairman of the Organizing Committee, Suresh Kalmadi and other high officials³⁹

3. The Coal block allotment scam Yet another scam that blew up on the face of the UPA government recently was the coal block allotment scam. Here the Comptroller and Auditor General of India accused the Government of India of acting in an arbitrary manner to allot coal blocks to private parties which resulted in a national loss of Rs.186,000 crore. Instead of competitive bidding, the government went in for selective allocation resulting in this huge loss. The losses in Coalgate surpassed that of spectrumgate⁴⁰.

India's rank in the global transparency index. Corruption is now a national disease. It is spreading like cancer in society. India is now listed as one of the most corrupt countries of the world in the yearly rankings of countries Transparency International. In 2011, India's position in dropped 11 places to 95th⁴¹. As Rukshana Nanayakkara, Transparency International's Senior Programme Coordinator for South Asia, aptly observed, "Although

India boasts a larger democratic space for public activism in countering corruption and opacity, little commitment has been delivered on the government's part for substantive eradication" ⁴²

Cure for corruption. So, how can corruption be cured? I think the first step that should be taken is to make people aware of corruption. And a strong social movement should be launched to raise public awareness. Though Anna Hazare's movement has been derided as anti-democratic, undermining the legitimacy of democratic institutions, (e.g., Panikkar, 2011) there is no doubt that his movement has brought the issue of corruption to the forefront in public discourse and ways and means are being discussed to solve the problem. Panikkar (2011: 43-44) has himself suggested two remedies which I think may be fruitfully applied to solve the problem. Firstly, fundamental changes in the administrative procedures are needed. Instead of secrecy, administrative procedures should be transparent. Secondly, decentralization of power and decision making are needed so that responsibility becomes collectivized. [Rukshana Nanayakkara](#) rightly observed: "If the 21st century is to truly be Asia's as predicted, comprehensive actions are needed to increase integrity and structural equality throughout the region. But to do this, governments and civil society must work together to counter corruption effectively" 43.

DISCUSSION

We have seen that the current phase of globalization has its roots in the neo-liberal philosophy. In his address to the closing session of the Fifth Meeting on Globalization and Development held in Havana, Cuba, on February 14, 2003, Fidel Castro rightly observed: "Neo-liberal globalization constitutes the most blatant recolonization of the Third World". (Castro 2003:18. **Bold italics mine**). Under pressure from the USA and western countries, India emerged on a path of 'reforms' from 1991 onwards and these reforms are continuing. According to 2010 List by KOF Index of Globalization, India ranked 111 out of 181 countries⁴⁴. Former Indian President, K.R. Narayan, in his address to the concluding function of the Asian Social Forum on 7th January, 2003 observed. "Reforms are necessary but for whom and for what"? He rightly said that reforms should benefit the people, and provide them employment⁴⁵ (**Bold italics mine**). But with regard to employment, we find that our elected UPA government is doing is the exact opposite of what the former Indian President had advocated. Under the stewardship of the second UPA government, India is more and more opening up its economy to western finance capital, ostensibly to encourage economic development and employment. Recently, the government has thrown open the retail sector to 51% Foreign Direct Investment India had already an unemployment rate of 9.4% in

201046. With the retail sector opened to foreign finance capital, millions of retail traders may see their livelihoods vanish. With regard to higher education, I agree with those who say that second rate or third rate foreign universities may open shop in India. They will become foreign islands in the sea of Indian higher education. They will produce graduates who will be schooled in foreign culture. Already western education is producing youth who are alienated from their own culture. The gap between masses and these educated youths will widen. Moreover, with the market dominating higher education, only those who can afford to spend massively on education will benefit. Poor but meritorious students will be shown the door. Globalization may be held responsible for the rising industrial unrest in contemporary

India. The recent events at Maruti are a pointer in this direction. And, above all, globalization in India has been accompanied by widespread corruption. The numerous scams attest to this fact.

Thanks to Globalization, Indian society has become beset with innumerable contradictions. India is the 3rd richest country in Asia and the fourth richest in the world.

47Our GDP is \$4, 060, 000,000,000 48. But The Economist: Worldwide Quality-of-life index, 2005, ranked India a poor 73 out of 111 countries⁴⁹..The United Nations: Human Development Index 2010, ranked India 119 out of 177 countries⁵⁰. Further research is needed to understand these contradictions in Indian society.

CONCLUDING REMARKS

In this lecture, I discussed some key contemporary issues regarding globalization in India, namely, (1) Globalization & Employment (2) Globalization & Higher Education (3) Globalization & Industrial Unrest (4) Globalization & FDI in retail (5) Globalization & Corruption.

Globalization has not and is not likely to have any beneficial impact on various sectors of Indian society. We have seen that globalization, and its attendant features like privatization, withdrawal of subsidies from essential commodities, including agricultural inputs like fertilizers, the ushering in of FDI in manufacturing, higher education, retail, etc., have opened the floodgates to inflation, corruption, industrial unrest and alienation of youth from their native culture. In future inequalities are likely to increase with consequent intensification of social unrest. Will the process of Globalization in India see society split into two great classes –the haves and the have not's? In that case Marx and Engels prophecy made in the Communist Manifesto (1848) will be fulfilled. If Indian society is to develop for the all round benefit of the people, as our former President K.R. Narayan advocated, we will need an alternative philosophy of development, which will have its roots in our indigenous culture and tradition.

NOTES

1. Vide New York Times, January 8, 1991; <http://www.nytimes.com/business/index.html>.
2. Vide Albert Christopher Dhas and Mary Jacqueline Helen: "Impact of Globalisation and Economic Reforms on Employment in India", Munic Personal Repec Archive 10th August, 2008, Table No.1.
3. Dhas and Helen, loc. cit.
4. Cited in T. E. Raja Simhan 'Slowdown dampens the job-hopping' [http://www.thehindubusinessline.com/industry-and-economy/info-tech/article3836448.ece? homepage=true](http://www.thehindubusinessline.com/industry-and-economy/info-tech/article3836448.ece?homepage=true)).
5. Vide Mithilesh Kumar Singh, "Globalization & Higher Education in India" <http://www.aserf.org.in/presentations/globalization.pdf> .
6. Mithilesh Kumar Singh, loc.cit.
7. "Globalization and Higher Education: Eight Common Perceptions From University Leaders" <http://www.anienetwork.org/content/globalization-and-higher-education-eight-common-perceptions-university->
8. Vide http://articles.economictimes.indiatimes.com/2006-12-05/news/27426732_1_operation-of-foreign-universities-e)
9. Ibid.
10. Mithilesh Kumar Singh, loc.cit.
11. T K Rohit: "The return of labour unrest" in The Times of India, July 26,2010, <http://timesofindia.indiatimes.com/business/india-business/The-return-of-labour-unrest/articleshow/6216532.cms>
12. T K Rohit, loc.cit.
13. Ibid.
14. See T.K. Rajalakshmi: 'Out of gear' in Frontline, Vol. 29, No.16, August 11-24,2012, .Panini Anand: "The Autopsy" in Outlook, Vol. LII. No.31, etc.
15. T.K Rohit et.al "The return of labour unrest" in The Times of India, July 26,2010.<http://timesofindia.indiatimes.com/business/india-business/The-return-of-labour-unrest/articleshow/6216532.cms>).
16. Cited in T.K Rohit et. al loc. cit .

17. Cited in T.K Rohit et.al.
18. For the full story see, T.K. Rajalakshmi: 'Out of gear' in Frontline, Vol. 29, No. 16, August 11-24, 2012, pp.28. See also Panini Anand: "The Autopsy" in Outlook, Vol. LII. No.31.pp. 26-33.
19. <http://www.thehindubusinessline.com/companies/article3836095.ece>
20. Se Sujan Dutta: "Guns to protect Maruti managers" – Report in The Telegraph, Calcutta, pp. 1 & 4.
21. See Santosh N Gambhire, Ajitsingh K Patil, Anurag Sinha: "Turning The Tide of Labour Unrest in India" indianmba.com, based on email dated September 1, 2005).
22. Business India, 27 July, 2012, http://www.moneycontrol.comnewsbusinessindia-not-to-change-decisionfdiretail-sharma_736550.html.
23. Govt. notifies FDI in retail: PM may address the nation today" – Report in Hindusthan Times, 26 September, 2012.
24. Cited in Ibid.
25. Cited in Shamik Ghosh ed."Foreign Direct Investment in Multi-brand retail :Who said what" (<http://www.ndtv.com/article/india/foreign-direct-investment-in-multi-brand-retail-aviation-who-said-what-267443>)
26. Ibid.
27. Cited in 'Farmers hail FDI in retail as politicians continue to fight' in <http://ibnlive.in.com/news/farmers-hail-fdi-as-politicians-continue-to-fight/291931-3.html>
28. Law Services: Foreign Direct Investment in Retail
29. Vide Law Services: Foreign Direct Investment in Retail, investment-retail-fdi.php .
30. (Vide Economic Times, July 30,2012 http://articles.economictimes.indiatimes.com/2012-07-30/news/32942310_1_multi-brand-fdi-lobby-issue)
31. Cited in "Walmart scandal in Mexico points to US Hypocrisy" in The Daily Beast April 23, 2012.
32. James Stewart: "Bribes without jailtime" in New York Times, ([bribes-but-little-jail-time-common-sense.html?pagewanted=all](http://www.nytimes.com/2012/04/23/us/politics/walmart-scandal-in-mexico-points-to-us-hypocrisy.html?_r=1)).
33. Ibid.
34. See "Walmart scandal in Mexico points to US Hypocrisy" in The Daily Beast April 23,2012.
35. Ibid.
36. Vide 'Traders to Observe 'Quit FDI Day' , Indian Express, 25 July,2012,p.13.
37. Cited in <http://www.ndtv.com/article/india/2g-scam-how-raja-allegedly-robbed-india->

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38. <http://www.thehindu.com>.

39. Vide. <http://www.business-standard.com/india/news/kalmadi-two-others-arrested-in-commonwealth-games-scam/433564/>.

40. See Alok Ray: "Core issues in ine coal scam" The Hindu Businessline, August 27, 2012.

41. See ET Bureau "Transparency International Corruption Index: India Drops to 95th Position," Economic Times, December 2, 2011 (http://articles.economictimes.indiatimes.com/2011-12-02/news/30467987_1_corrupt-country-australia-shares-cases)

42. Rukshana Nanayakkara, "2011 Corruption Perceptions Index: Alarming results in Asia" (<http://blog.transparency.org/2011/11/30/2011-corruption-perceptions-index-alarming-results-in-asia/>)

43. Rukshana Nanayakkara, loc.cit.

44. Vide Wikipedia.

45. Narayan cited in "Asia must fight Globalization:Narayan" – Report in Teachers of the World, Vol.4, No. 2, p. 10.

46. Vide Wikipedia.

47. Ibid.

48. Ibid.

49. Ibid.

50. Ibid.

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